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Bifacial Energy Gain of Photovoltaic Arrays Installed on Highly Reflective Rooftops

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Purpose of the work

- Analysis of the bifacial gain installed on highly reflective rooftops
- 3D evaluation of the rear irradiance to consider non homogenous distribution
- Identification of the key parameters (modules elevation, row distance) that have an influence in the bifacial energy gain
- Cell level irradiance distribution and breakdown per component (diffuse and direct)
- Evaluate albedo characteristics and evolution (soiling) influence

Methodology overview

Detailed 3D scenario

Proprietary tool to model the details of the 3D installation including fixations, modules distribution, material reflection properties...

GPU based rendering engine

- Local spherical view image generation to perform different analysis (sky shading, diffuse and irradiance breakdown contribution...)
- GPU rendering engine to obtain high resolution definition at a fraction of time of ray tracing techniques (2-3 ms per spherical view generated)

Detailed albedo

- BRDF defined through 3 relative angles
- Soiling effect

Results & applications

Roof surface reflective potential for diffuse irradiance

- Low tilt angle and proximity to the roof reduce the effective diffuse reflection potential
- Row distance increase improves the diffuse reflection potential but reduces the CGR of the installation

Time dependent evaluation for direct irradiance

- Direct irradiance is highly dependent on sun position and location of the cell in the module (top – summer, bottom – winter)
- Detailed evaluation of the direct irradiance is done through the analysis of a highly detailed spherical view of the environment on specific locations of the module

Non homogeneous irradiance distribution on the back side

- Both diffuse (top) and direct irradiance contribution present a noticeable border effect
- Border effect on direct irradiance contribution is very time dependent (summer morning shown)
- Majority of the module area receives a very reduced contribution